

SKULL BUNNY!: THE VISION BEHIND A SCI-FI STORY

by

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I. Introduction

Throughout my life as a creative, my artistic visions have been primarily inspired by forms of Japanese and Western animated media with Japanese animation, especially Studio Trigger's earlier works (and currently *Brand New Animal* and *Cyberpunk: Edgerunners*) being the backbone of my visual and storytelling abilities. My original sci-fi fantasy story, *Skull Bunny!*, not only pays homage to my creative upbringing, but also aims to evoke emotions in its audience through its storytelling, colorful visuals, as well as through underlying messages. As of now, it is being developed and produced as a webcomic on WEBTOON since it is the most accessible format for me to publish my original ideas onto. When I have the resources and budget, I may have plans to adapt the webcomic into an indie animation series of television-length episodes (minimum of 12 minutes) published to digital streaming services, such as YouTube. I am thinking of the indie genre since it is not only accessible to share online, but also because I feel as if I would still have the creative freedom to share my visions for the story. However, I believe I will still be open to publishing the media to a company, such as allowing it to be streamed on services such as Netflix.

II. Story

The story of *Skull Bunny!* illustrates the life of Bunny Anemone (full name being Amy Anemone), who is excited to move into a brand new city all on her own. However, her life is turned upside down as she suddenly unlocks a mysterious power, leading to a group investigation

about its origins. The journey to the answer won't be easy, as there is a masked threat lurking nearby.

Set during the 22nd century, a majority of humankind resides in the capital of Ume City, located on a distant planet dubbed New Earth. Bunny travels far with her starry-eyed friend, Allen “Joe” Anthurium, to the heart of the city in order to chase her dreams of attending an elite university while Joe aims to set up his musical debut in the city square. One day, during a casual outing in the famous park of Ume City, Bunny comes across a peculiar flower that seems to call her name. Despite Joe’s warnings to not touch anything as it goes against park rules, the wide-eyed college student reaches out towards that flower, which exerts a blinding force against her, with her gaining a newfound supernatural ability to manipulate plants. Roselia “Skull” Norcross, the poster girl of the Vanguard, witnesses this, and after receiving an unknown order from her higher ups, she offers Amy a job as the organization’s patrol team with the purpose of investigating the origins of her mysterious ability. The duo of Skull and Bunny undergo many trials and tribulations of stopping crime and keeping the city safe, as well as Bunny learning valuable life lessons about the world she lives in.

However, Skull eventually discovers a hidden piece of history that would prove to be essential to uncovering a lurking threat to Bunny’s safety. From the scribbled text of a worn book amongst the ruined archives underneath the Vanguard headquarters, it states that back on the original planet of Earth, during the late 21st century, the human population was dwindling. Drastic levels of pollution and disease had rendered Earth as an inhabitable planet. Scientists have discovered a planet of flowers in a nearby solar system that was slowly becoming habitable. Dr. Cain, a notable scientist at the time, took into account the chances of survival of the human race, and considered the use of colonization technologies she developed to ensure the survival of

the human race. After the government discovered technologies she had created without the knowledge of others, Dr. Cain decided to carry through her colonization plan. Resources would be incredibly expensive to support everyone, thus more than half of the global population was left behind.

Dr. Cain had successfully helped the migration of the human race. While dealing with the extensive research of genetic modification, she had wanted to free civilization of greed. The population was fairly small as the modifications had prevented potential mothers from giving birth. Thus, society was initially agricultural and had relied on a point-based system. However, as the distribution of artificial aids spread, The population increased, leading to the exhaustion and expenses of supplies.

Unfortunately, Dr. Cain's life was cut short by the actions of her sister, Carrie Cain, who sought to take her place in fame instead. Carrie had shadowed her sister's work that led to the successful human migration to the new planet, which was codenamed "Ume" at the time. Carrie also had arranged a secret meeting with the legislature of scientists and rich government officials at the time, both parties agreeing to stage Quark Cain's death. She held a personal grudge towards her own sibling and was resentful since she felt as if no credit was given to her name, and that all the credit was passed onto her sister instead. She wanted to be the one who was adored. The other party, the elite scientists who were closer colleagues to Carrie, weren't fans of Dr. Cain's growing contributions either, feeling threatened by the speculation that one day, Dr. Cain would be the ultimate ruler of everyone in the world. They wanted to regain some of their power and influence back.

Thus, aggravated by the lack of scientific recognition from the elites and public, along with criticizing the former point-based system, Carrie invited her sister to a one-on-one meeting

at their second house, located miles away from the developing city. After Carrie lashes out and violently expresses her jealousy towards her sister, she incapacitates her, subsequently setting fire to the house. She premeditated the murder of her sibling to bury the name of Dr. Cain as much as she could. She even made sure that even the elite scientists covered up the truth behind the murder too, lying to the public about how her sister passed away due to an unknown terminal illness.

As a result, society reverted to a state of capitalism, discriminating against those who were deemed “poor” through various actions, such as wealthy families refusing to offer shelter and instead quoting how “they would waste our resources and bankrupt the survivability of humankind once more.” A few decades later, many towns and small cities were established. Ume City, the pinpoint location of mankind’s first steps on New Earth, was deemed the capital city.

It is eventually revealed that Bunny’s supernatural ability was the passed down result of the rare side effects of the human modifications installed by Dr. Cain many decades ago, and so Bunny’s strength was amplified by the presence of flowers. Bloom bullets, invented by Carrie’s nephew during Bunny’s time, were intended to absorb those abilities, which were also used to inject the powers into whoever. Thus, Carrie was the ultimate threat to Bunny who sought to forcefully take the power for herself. In addition, Ume City was where Cain had developed her human improvement project as it was built on a vast prairie of flowers, enhancing the outcome of these modifications. At the unfortunate timing of this discovery, Skull and Bunny receive sudden news of Camelia (Skull’s estranged younger sister), who is Ume City’s most famous (and infamous for her extreme acts posted on social media) popstar, at the highest level of the Vanguard Headquarters, live streaming her martyrish attempt to bomb not only the Vanguard, but herself as well.

As Bunny races to stop Camelia, Skull confronts Carrie at the basement level of the building with a newfound sense of rage and disbelief. Carrie only solidifies the fact, revealing her contempt towards her late ancestor, Dr. Cain, as she stated that genetic modifications provided a sense of unfairness to those who either did or did not have flower power. Because she also lived a life full of hate, she dedicated her studies towards the creation of bloom bullets. Additionally, Carrie was found to be terrified of the idea of her sister coming back for vengeance. She saw a lot of her sister's traits in Bunny, a lot which caused her to see Bunny as essentially another clone of Dr. Cain. The similarities between the bright-eyed Dr. Cain and happy-go-lucky Bunny were so accurate in Carrie's eyes that she concluded that her own sister was somehow reincarnated in order to eventually murder her too. She was growing increasingly paranoid and desperate in her efforts to murder Bunny, motivated by the fear of being exposed to her past terrible crime.

The series ends as Bunny and Skull fend Carrie off, both deliberately detonating the bomb in the Vanguard's science and engineering facility as a last attempt to stop Carrie from murdering Bunny. As the last of Bunny's power wears off, she lays still as her body, which once benefitted from the ability, immediately exhausts itself. At the end of the story, Bunny regains consciousness due to Joe gently waking her in an ICU in the local hospital, being informed that Roselia is tending to her sister, Camelia, in another room.

III. Underlying Messages

Bunny's power is meant to be a symbolic representation of her voice. It can also parallel our universe, in which we need our voice in order to make a change in a system, just as how

Bunny's voice is needed to make a change in exposing Carrie's dictatorship of the Vanguard. In general, Bunny would not have made it alive if she did not have the fortunate help of other people she meets throughout the story, such as Skull. Although Skull was a part of the Vanguard, she still managed to amplify Bunny's voice in the end, helping her expose Carrie's dangerous intentions to secure the power.

The media includes commentary on the system of capitalism as well. For instance, the historical sequence of Dr. Cain's societal improvements and her efforts being abruptly cut short due to avarice, were inspired by multiple personal witness accounts of promises being overshadowed and eventually dropped by interests in profit. Overall, this shares an underlying message of how focus towards mere financial and power gain impacts groups of lower hierarchy in a community. Furthermore, Dr. Cain and Carrie Cain's story alludes to the tale of Julius Caesar's demise, specifically of how Carrie fought to become a figure who would be far more popular than her late sister. I wanted to take this opportunity to showcase how dangerous greed and the obsessive pursuit towards power can be and how it can lead to unfortunate and lethal consequences.

Somewhere in the whole story, I plan to include key facts that illustrate the bitter relation between Skull and her sister, Camelia, that can also parallel the bitterness between Carrie and Dr. Cain's sister connection too. Skull and Camelia's upbringing and how their bitter relationship is a consequence of the wealthy separating them is a result of the system. Essentially, Skull and Camelia grew up in a lower income family who placed pressure on the two to have some sort of successful career, even at their young age. Because of how Skull was often overlooked and how Camelia was the most paid attention to, Camelia wanted to sustain her positive reputation amongst her family, even if it meant reaching higher and higher. Yet, Skull's talent in

sharpshooting led to the main city's developing rich paramilitary group, the Vanguard, to recruit her at the young age of 18, dubbing her a young prodigy. As Skull set off to permanently move to the city, the Norcross family looked down upon Camelia, calling her a failure, and Camelia grew resentful towards her sibling just how Carrie grew resentful for not feeling as if she was recognized by the public. Unbeknownst to Camelia, Skull is still being trapped by the city's intense expectations of her to be constantly honing her aim and fighting abilities.

Even though Camelia is the world's most popular model, Carrie being the overarching head of the Vanguard and the city government, Dr. Cain being recognized for her efforts, and Skull being the best paramilitary figure, all of them still don't feel as if their titles have accomplished enough. The system cultivated environments for these women, stirring pressure among communities for their members to forever work tirelessly to generate some sort of gain and profit from them.

The series critiques on power in today's society with Carrie's position as the head of all government and the Vanguard, generally exploring why her existing power is still not satiable for her personal needs. Her looming power over the city works as an underlying message of how she constantly searches for the right amount of validation from the people beneath her, as if she is cursed to forever be starved of not being enough or being loud enough to voice how much she contributed to the world. Being a planned addition to the story, the Vanguard's recruitment of Bunny also plays into this message as it entraps her to undergo countless seemingly trivial missions to keep her supernatural power in check and under its control, using her initial obliviousness to steer her away from the harsh truth as much as it could until the climax of the plot.

IV. Conclusion

I have had this story envisioned back in 2018, creating drafts of character designs and have had multiple revisions of the story, and I am excited to develop it further into a webcomic (and possibly into a television show length series) for others to enjoy a fun story.

V. Postscript

I would like to share my developing designs of some of the characters to further my storytelling in the series below.

Skull “Roselia” Norcross

PHYSIOLOGY

Species: Human

Age: 23

Gender: Female

Marks or defects: High ponytail and dark lipstick

Likeness/metaphor: She's like a lone wolf

PSYCHOLOGY

Conscious want: Wants to protect her city

Subconscious need: Wants to find a love that won't leave her side

Conscious fear: Seeing someone she wants to protect get hurt

Subconscious fear: Being a useless tool

Main strength: Her excellent sharpshooter skills

Main weakness: Her lacking skills in melee combat

Temperament: Reserved and stern

Moral Values: Loyal connection to the government

Events in her past: She grew up in a small town, being under the care of her veteran parents. Her interest and talent in shooting targets led her to become a child prodigy of combat, leading her to be discovered and recruited by the developing city's paramilitary at the age of 18. After 5 years of being mentored by a notable figure who goes by the name Alice Jackson, Skull starts to wonder what her purpose in life really is.

Alice Jackson

PHYSIOLOGY

Species: Human

Age: 60

Gender: Female

Marks: Eyebags and dark circles

Likeness/metaphor: She's like a tall skunk

PSYCHOLOGY

Conscious want: Wants to watch the world burn from the sidelines

Subconscious need: Needs morality and human connection

Main strength: Her lower body strength and melee combat skills

Main weakness: Her lack of human understanding

Temperament: Sly and laidback

Moral values: Strength overpowering all

Events in her past: Ever since she witnessed the burning of her orphanage, she was left to survive alone in the nearby city with the practice of thievery and deception. After being discovered and recruited by the paramilitary of the city, she climbs the ranks due to her talent in combat and eventually becomes a renowned member. However, her focus on fighting leads her to find no importance in human connection, which causes her to neglect the emotion of others.

HMPH.

HMM...

FUFUFU

I designed these characters, Skull and Alice, in a manner where I aim to show the effects of working in a tough organization, such as the Vanguard, and how amplified focus of monetary and powerful gain can impact their emotional states and demeanors. For their aesthetics, I aim to not only show the simple fashion of their era, but also to show shape language too. For instance, Skull's overall shapes are composed of squares to symbolize her masculine build and her unchanging views of how she always must be the best, while Alice's overall design consists of triangular forms, symbolizing her erratic but quick actions in melee combat along with her perplexing views on the world and human emotions.